

CULTURE AND HERITAGE TOURISM IN THE MODERN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

The following article discusses the phenomenon of “cultural tourism” and summarizes its importance in the development of modern world.

Key words. Culture tourism, national heritage, subcategory, intercultural perception, national and cultural mentality.

Expanding the term “cultural tourism”, it is necessary to define the concept of “culture” in terms of tourism. It can be considered as “a historically defined level of development of man and society, a wide sphere of human activity, which includes conservation, transmission from generation to generation and use of the national heritage, accounting of the world culture, careful interaction with nature”. If tourism is defined as the totality of different types of travel (tourist routes, trips) for certain purposes, then the direction of “cultural tourism” can be described as the travelling of people in order to get acquainted with both their own and other cultures. Any kind of tourism to some extent is cultural, because throughout traveling, a tourist experiences the influence of an unusual socio-cultural environment. Accordingly, in this case, the cultural aspect of tourism is under the consideration, that is, – “the impact that tourism affects the material and spiritual spheres human activities and, above all, on his system of values, knowledge and social behavior”.

Based on above mentioned understanding of the phenomenon of “cultural tourism”, researchers⁴³ distinguish five subcategories of culture tourism: 1) professional, 2) specialized, 3) non-specialized, 4) accompanying and 5) cultural quasi-tourism (the movement of residents in a given area, one of the motives of which is consumption of cultural goods). According to the degree of priority of special cultural interest, spiritual needs and aesthetic satisfaction received, each tourist trip can be attributed to one of the above listed subcategories.

Tourism is particularly attractive aesthetic and emotional aspects of travel. The historical and cultural environment draws people into their own unusual world. That is

why the main condition for the development of cultural tourism is the historical and cultural potential of a certain country, the national heritage of the people, in general, tourist resources located on specific territory. In the process of social interaction caused by contacts between cultures, relationships of different nature arise, in largely, determined by the national and cultural mentality of representatives of different countries.

The results of studying the processes intercultural perception, conducted by N.K. Ikonnikova is worth to be discussed. She identifies three stages of interaction, which indicate qualitative changes in the process of perceiving culture. The first stage is defined as the “honeymoon”. This is a period of acquaintance with a new culture, its individual achievements or representatives, which gives rise to a surge of optimism, high spirits, and confidence in a successful interaction and a problem-free perspective on future. The second stage is defined as “cultural shock” and is characterized by the collapse of hopes, rejection of new customs, behavioral style and communication norms, inability to pace of life, changes in the material infrastructure of society, etc. The last stage forms a realistic assessment of the situation, when there is an adequate understanding of what is happening, the ability to effectively achieve one's own goals. However, the possibility of complete rejection cannot be ruled out new cultural phenomena and the inevitable this case retreat. As N. K. Ikonnikova notes, the duration of contact is of great importance. The longer the tourist “interacts” with the unfamiliar culture, the more time he has to get to know it. This psychological moment is very important for the successful development of tourism.

In addition, the development of tourism should take place with minimal impact on the natural livelihoods of the local population. In this case, we can talk about a different understanding of the term “cultural tourism”. First of all, it introduces historical monuments and cultural objects. At the same time from the point in terms of the nature of the course of this socio-cultural action, cultural tourism can be characterized as “soft”, preserving and protecting the type of tourism. In this case, this type of tourism is determined not so much by the characteristics of the object as by the subject. It expresses the level of perception and awareness of the tourist surrounding reality, his or her desire to get the most out of life, to live several “cultural” lives in one “location”. Thus, cultural tourism characterizes the correspondence of the cultural level of the tourist to the historical and cultural values chosen by him for acquaintance. If in general tourism seems more like a part of leisure pastime and does not require certain knowledge and skills, then cultural tourism implies a certain level of education. Cultural values and aesthetic experiences are the main incentives for such a journey. At the same time, the latter

is viewed not only as a result (meeting tourist and cultural object), but also as a process perception and comprehension of the value-semantic contents of another culture. It is cultural tourism that most contributes to the manifestation of ethno-cultural identity and individuality of a person and is the best way of his/her self-expression. Giving preference to one or another route of travel, a person makes a conscious choice, which determined only by his personal needs and wishes.

In this case, tourism, as already noted, acts as one of the forms of intercultural contacts, which allows a person to temporarily immerse himself in other cultures, contributes to the development of, on the one hand, a clearer understanding of the diversity of our world (international tourism) and awareness of the value and identity of their own culture, on the other hand (domestic tourism). Therefore, tourism is effective means of mass exchange of sociocultural experience that in the conditions of the transformation of the world into a “unity of diversity” is a necessity.

In the era of high technologies and in the context of the integration of financial and political systems in united exchange of cultural information becomes an important factor in the successful development of a person, community, state. If in other areas of modern society, standardization is necessary and, possibly, quantitative measurement parameters, then for the cultural sphere this is unacceptable. The culture of any nation is original and unique, therefore cultural tourism is able to act as a means of mutual understanding and mutually beneficial relations between different cultures.

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